

Diversity and Inclusion for Digital Humanists (Proposal for Ottawa 2020)

This workshop seeks to create awareness of diversity and cultural differences, as well as to present strategies for successful inclusion and the development of fairer environments. These factors are especially important within the Digital Humanities because of its emphasis on collaborative work which brings together different individuals. Moreover, our work has shown that in Digital Humanities, where there could be many different voices, most of the power and prestige remain centralized in the Global-North, in Anglophone countries.¹ This is not surprising considering the general state of academia as a mostly male, mostly white environment (Johnsrud and Des Jarlais 1994, Townsend 2013). For this reason, it's essential to work with individuals to foster a richer environment, to change behaviours, and to challenge prejudices.

Reflecting on these matters also allows us to expand the horizons of our own limited perspectives. An article published in the Scientific American, "How Diversity Makes Us Smarter," states:

Decades of research by organizational scientists, psychologists, sociologists, economists and demographers show that socially diverse groups (that is, those with a diversity of race, ethnicity, gender and sexual orientation) are more innovative than homogeneous groups. (Phillips 2014)

In DH, creativity and innovation are essential for the development of new approaches or new applications of traditional methodologies. O'Donnell has argued that diversity is a core value in Digital Humanities:

"Diversity"—in the sense of access to as wide a possible range of experiences, contexts, and purposes in the computational context of or application of computation to the study of problems in the Humanities, *particularly as this is represented by the lived*

¹ Although the community has been making efforts to raise awareness via different statements on inclusion (DHSI Statement on Ethics and Inclusion <http://www.dhsi.org/events.php>
ADHO Code of Conduct <http://adho.org/administration/conference-coordinating-program-committee/adho-conference-code-conduct>
EADH Diversity and Inclusivity <http://eadh.org/about/diversity-and-inclusivity>
ACH Statement after the 2016 election <https://ach.org/activities/advocacy/ach-statement-in-the-aftermath-of-the-2016-election/>
CSDH/SCHN Inclusivity and Diversity Statement <https://csdh-schn.org/inclusivity-and-diversity-statement/>), these efforts have become part of what we call "the diversity paradox" where success in recognizing there is a problem might often be construed as an achieved solution (See Ahmed 2017, 103).

experiences of different demographic groups—is in fact *more* important than “Quality,” especially if “Quality” is determined using methods that encourage the reinscription of already dominant forms of research and experience. (O’Donnell, forthcoming).

The first version of this workshop was commissioned by Karina Van Dalen-Oskan in 2016 to be delivered to the members of ADHO’s steering committee. We delivered a first version of the workshop at the 2017 DH in Montreal 2017, and a second one in Mexico City 2018. A third version, at which we unveiled a new game we have developed to promote the goals of this workshop, was adjudicated, accepted and presented at DH 2019, Utrecht. These experiences have shown the workshop topic is a moving target as community norms adjust and change (thus, for example, we have seen an increasing interest in diversity of gender expression in our workshops even over the last two years). In light of the last two workshops, we have modified and updated the content and activities for this proposal.

Contents:

1. Diversity

Different concepts of diversity, with particular emphasis on cultural and contextual differences.

2. Implicit Bias and Cultural Cloning

Notions of implicit bias (an unconscious and automatic reflex causing us to pass judgement on others) and Cultural Cloning (the tendency for replication of hiring committees where people of the same ethnicity, ability, gender, etc hire people like themselves [Essed & Goldberg 2002, Essed 2004]).

The impact of Implicit Bias on teachers and educators, hiring committees and other bodies making decisions about others (journal editors, grant evaluators). We carry out exercises on implicit bias awareness, something which has been shown to have

3. Privilege

To work on the concept of privilege we have developed a game which we use to illustrate the many factors shaping our lives. Particularly in the case of privileged individuals, it is not easy to locate and categorize their own instances of privilege. In collaboration with the [Huygens Institute](#) (The Netherlands), we have developed a digital version of the privilege game to be used as a training tool during our workshops (<https://privilege.huc.knaw.nl>). The game can be played in group or solo modes and the questions can be modified for particular sets of circumstances.

4. Intersectionality (in contraposition to the notion of kyriarchy)

When two or more oppressive systems overlap and negatively impact an individual, we talk about intersectionality (Crenshaw 1991, Essed 1994, Essed & Goldberg 2002 Risam 2005). This core concept allows us to explore how privilege or lack thereof impacts individuals directly.

5. Inclusion solutions

Through guided group activities, we facilitate the identification of “inclusion solutions” which participants can implement or propose in their institutions, projects, or other work environments.

At the end of this workshop, we aim to guide participants to reflect on the benefits of a more diverse working environment by questioning our preconceived notions of sameness as an ideal.

Discussions in the context of this workshop deal with various delicate subjects and, for this reason, individuals are likely to experience bonding within their working groups. We consider this a fortunate side effect of the workshop.

The workshop is directed at anyone with an interest in understanding diversity in digital humanities and creating a welcoming and inclusive DH environment. Conference organizers, leaders in the field, and those who often form part of hiring committees are invited to participate. Everyone is welcome to attend, but we particularly encourage the participation of people who are in privileged positions in academia, GLAM, or similar environments.

The workshop is led by **Barbara Bordalejo** (University of Saskatchewan, 9 Campus Drive, Saskatoon, SK S7N 5A5, Canada. +1 306 371 0578. barbara.bordalejo@usask.ca) and **Daniel Paul O'Donnell** (University of Lethbridge, English Department, A840 University Hall, 4401 University Drive, Lethbridge, Alberta T1K 3M4, +1 403 3292377. daniel.odonnell@uleth.ca) It requires a data projector with audio, as well as internet access.

The activities are self-financing, we do not require participants to pay registration **and believe strongly that they should also not be charged for this particular workshop.**

This version of the workshop is half-day or four hours, with capacity for no more than sixty people. We worked with 47 participants in 2017, and with 25 in 2018.

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